

Ebola: A latent threat to Latin America. Are we ready?

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1 LETTER TO THE EDITOR

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3 **Ebola: a latent threat to Latin America. Are we ready?**

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9 **Ebola: a latent threat to Latin America. Are we ready?**

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11 Recently, European governments have been summoned to mobilize resources to
12 attend the Ebola outbreak in West Africa [1]. Along these lines, we think we should
13 also urge Latin American (LA) governments to contribute to halt this humanitarian
14 crisis and to be prepared for the potential arrival of this deadly virus in the
15 Caribbean, Central and South American mainland.

16

17 Regarding the collaboration to intervene the crises, it is important to highlight that
18 the Cuban government has already sent a team of 165 highly trained health-care
19 professionals to assist and mitigate the epidemic –this is, so far, the largest
20 medical team that any single foreign country has sent out to the field [2]. Following
21 this effort we encourage other LA governments to create a package of incentives –
22 i.e. paid temporary leave– to facilitate the mobilization of qualified health care
23 professionals to the West Africa region.

24

25 In the preparedness to attend the probable arrival of Ebola to the LA region, we
26 acknowledge a huge need for field-based laboratories, epidemiological and
27 microbiological surveillance resources, diagnostic equipment, and mobile
28 communications software as well as other technological assets. As revealed by the
29 ongoing Chikungunya epidemic, Latin America is particularly vulnerable given that
30 there is a lack of appropriate health care infrastructure to tackle a challenge of
31 such dimensions. In addition, highly densely populated poverty areas with deficient
32 basic services constitute a melting pot for the development of potential outbreaks.

33 Biosafety level-4 (BSL-4) laboratories in Latin America are scarce and some health
34 systems have been incapable to control tropical and endemic diseases, as recently
35 reported for malaria in Venezuela [3].

36

37 As opposed to Europe, where a European BSL-4 laboratories network already
38 exists [4], LA still requires a significant increase in technical partnership as well as
39 other resource capabilities, which in the past has limited the work with other
40 important BSL-4 required viral pathogens endemic to the region, such as
41 hantaviruses [5]. Even more, health care institutions should start joining efforts to
42 design preparedness and response programs in order to revamp or build up *de*
43 *novo* infrastructure to properly address suspicious cases and prepare healthcare
44 professionals for caring of confirmed Ebola infected patients.

45

46 If Ebola hits the jackpot in LA this would pose an immense diagnostic dilemma in a
47 region where indigenous viral hemorrhagic fevers exhibiting remarkable similar
48 clinical findings are endemic. Distinguishing cases of Guanarito (Venezuela),
49 Machupo (Bolivia), Junín (Argentina) and Sabiá (Brasil) viruses from Ebola, as well
50 as from other highly prevalent infections such as yellow fever, hemorrhagic
51 dengue, leptospirosis and typhoid amongst others will constitute an ever-increasing
52 challenge. Point of care testing using a biothreat panel like the BioFire diagnostics
53 BioSurveillance system would be very useful for screening highly suspicious cases,
54 while at the same time, providing an automated sample-to-answer diagnostic
55 platform in areas with lack of healthcare trained personnel. However we yet don't

56 know how such tests would perform in a non-prevalent Ebola region, and at the
57 same time it could be cost-prohibitive for many governments in the hemisphere.

58

59 Finally, it is also important to coordinate this LA response to Ebola with the
60 guidance of the regional multilateral health organisms: the *Pan-American Health*
61 *Organization* should lead this process; and the recently created *South-American*
62 *Institute of Government in Health* (www.isags-unasur.org) and the *South-American*
63 *National Institutes of Health Network* [6] could demonstrate their capacity to recruit
64 and materialize resources for global health.

65

66 As stated for Europe, we also fully expect all our LA governments to make up for
67 lost time with celerity, determination, and commitment. The Ebola epidemic
68 represents a public health imperative; unchecked, it might very well become a
69 geopolitical crisis; demanding instead of just words, actions.

70

71 **Conflict of interest**

72 None declared.

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